

City Parks as Urban Agroforestry

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An edible city park in urban recreational area in Joensuu, Finland (Photo: Tanja Kähkönen).

Urban forests, parks and other green areas promote public health and well-being, for instance living in urban areas with green space promotes physical activity and social interactions, contributes to recreational inhabitants needs, and addresses challenges that climate change poses such as a need for cooling of urban environments. Biodiverse environments have also been found to improve for instance children's immune systems which potentially reduces prevalence of some illness such as allergies.

Besides rural areas, agroforestry can be practiced also in urban areas. In different parts of Europe, agroforestry established in public spaces is used for i environmental education, as a measure to increase comfort in urban environments, as a method to create stronger community spirit, and in producing food. They also disguise urban landscapes and reduce wind negative effects.

In Finland, there are cities which have integrated agroforestry in their urban green space as homegardens. One of these cities is Joensuu in Eastern Finland, a vibrant city of nearly 80000 inhabitants, also named as the Forest Capital of Europe. Urban agroforestry managed by the city can be found in 24 different locations as edible parks: city parks, children's playgrounds, schools, and other public areas. Each location has a varying number of edible woody plants from one plant to over hundred of them with species such as aronia, currants, saskatoon berry, cherry, apple, plum, and crab apple planted among others. Although anyone can eat berries and fruit and harvest them also for own use, the amount of harvest can be limited due to low amount of edible woody plants in the location. The amount of harvest also varies depending on the development stage of each plant, damage by wildlife, and annual fluctuations. In the city of Joensuu, the edible parks function as an additional carbon storage in city parks, provide local food for inhabitants, and enhance biodiversity. Besides establishing edible parks, the city of Joensuu has also had forest grazing in some of its urban forests making the city one of the forerunners in urban agroforestry in Finland.

References

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